

Basic Steps of **ESE-TechProbe**

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Proposal

Tutorial on how to use and adapt ESE-TechProbe, a technique based on Technology Probe

Focus

Software engineers

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Overview

The ESE-TechProbe is based on the Technology Probe method and crafted for validation sessions. The technique is adequate if you are looking for a way to validate a technology proposal with end users, understand the user experience, and collect their feedback. The technique focuses on extracting results with sessions over a couple of hours and uses strategies to immerse the users in the context of technology use. The present document shows a couple of steps to apply for the ESE-TechProbe.

Step 0 – Is the ESE-TechProbe what you need?

Before planning and preparing your study, it is important to understand if this technique aligns with your goals. The next sections present questions to guide your decision.

What are your Motivations?

The ESE-TechProbe is an interesting approach if the research team is interested in gathering data regarding one of these aspects: eliciting design features, evaluating the technology's feasibility, collecting user feedback, gathering insights and ideas from the users, discovering unintended uses of the technology, or perceiving user reality.

What outcomes do you expect?

Using the ESE-TechProbe, diverse qualitative data regarding the proposed technology and the end-users can be gathered, specifically regarding the user experience, user feedback, and a list of specifications for improvements and requirements for the proposed technology.

Keep in mind some challenges.

Due to the Technology Probe's nature, the technique poses some challenges—for example, the engagement of end users and participation recruitment. The execution can also represent a challenge, maybe from the user profile or the time frame available for the evaluation. The ESE-TechProbe uses the user journey to mitigate this challenge, trying to immerse the user faster in the context to collect data about the probe in hours at most.

Step 1 – Planning the TP Session

1.1 Deploy the Probe

It is essential to have a **Probe**, an artifact you want to validate and discover user features. This probe can be technological (including software and/or hardware components) or non-technological (an abstraction of an idea you want to validate). Regardless of its nature, this probe needs to be ready for use so that users can interact with it. How it will be deployed is up to the research team.

1.2 Design User Journey

Given the necessity of immersing the participants in the reality of using the probe and the challenge of doing this in a validation session that lasts an hour, it is important to find ways to deal with this, such as user journeys. User journeys enable the participants to immerse themselves in a specific context of usage in a limited timeframe, allowing them to focus on one activity at a time.

It is important to be transparent to the participants at each step of their journey so they can fulfill the tasks and follow the think-aloud protocol accordingly. Finally, at the end of each journey step, they must complete a questionnaire that assesses their experience at that specific step and asks for suggestions to improve the process.

The following image shows the sequential structure of the user journey.

1.3 Prepare explanation material

The first step in the meeting with the participants is to explain the context in which the proposed technology (the probe) will be used. It is necessary to be cautious not to give much information about the probe to not bias the participants' ideas and suggestions. Then, it is imperative to prepare material (slides presentation, document..., etc.) to present this context to users. Also, it is important to explain the steps of the user journey the participants will go through.

1.4 Adequate Questionnaires

To collect the participant's perception, a collection of anonymous questionnaires is essential in different phases of the study: before the participant interacts with the probe (pre-session), after each step of the user journey (throughout the study), and when the interaction with the probe ends (post-session questionnaire).

1.4.1 Pre-session questionnaires

The pre-session questionnaire aims to collect consent from the participants, their demographic information (if the research team finds it interesting), and, most importantly, collect the participants' expectations regarding the probe. This questionnaire should be used after a brief explanation about the probe is given so that when participants are asked about their expectations, they have something to support their ideas.

The aim of asking their expectations is to promote creativity so that the researcher can use their answers to improve the technology.

An example of informed consent is seen in: [Informed consent Form](#)

An example of this questionnaire is seen in: [Pre-session questionnaire](#)

1.4.2 Throughout study questionnaires

The session will follow the user journey that was previously mapped, so whenever a step is completed, the participants should complete a questionnaire to assess their experience in the specific step (using the visual analogue scale) and reflect on improvements in the experience. The first question aims to understand the user's feelings and feedback about the usage of the probe, while the second wants to stimulate their creativity on the use of the proposed technology.

An example of the questionnaire can be seen in: [Post journey step questionnaire](#)

1.4.3 Post-session questionnaires

After the end of the user journey, the participants will be asked to answer a questionnaire to assess their opinions regarding the probe. At first, ask them to rate their overall experience with the probe. Then, they should qualify the technological proposal using a set of adjectives for them to choose. Finally, there will be open questions to catch positive and constructive feedback. Finally, there will be an open field for participants to write any final consideration they may have.

An example of the questionnaire can be seen in: [Post-session questionnaire](#)

1.5 Define Data Collection Strategy

Although the Technology Probe methodology leaves it up to the researchers to choose the strategy, the ESE-TechProbe uses a set of qualitative data: researcher filed notes gathered by their observation, annotations, and recordings of the participant's think-aloud and the data collected by the questionnaires, mostly end-user suggestions and ideas. In the case of a technological probe, using the probe log data to triangulate with the other data is valuable.

To help the researchers make their field notes, an instrument can be used keeping in mind the goals and aspects of Technology Probe (social, design, and engineering): [researcher notes](#)

1.6 Define Observation Strategy

The ESE-TechProbe proposes two options to guide the observation: **task execution** or **open-end probe interaction**. The first one can be applied given specific tasks for the participants to complete in each step of the journey, while the second one the participants use freely to complete the goal of the journey step.

Step 2 – Technology Probe Execution

After the planning, it's time to put into practice and execute the Technology Probe using the ESE-TechProbe. The arrangement of the study consists of three phases: pre-session, the session (moment of the participant intersecting with the probe using the think-aloud protocol) and the post-session. Further, the actions for each phase will be detailed.

2.1 Pre-session

The pre-session is a moment to align expectations with users. First, there should be an explanation of the probe, not giving too many details. Then, the participants should agree to the informed consent, answer the demographic questions, and register their expectations for the probe (that's why it shouldn't be given too much information about the probe at first). Finally, the researchers can explain the study's goal, presenting the user journey the user will go through for the next hour.

The researcher must remember to fill in the participant ID on the informed consent form and the subsequent form accordingly. This way, it will be possible to keep track of answers.

2.2 Interacting with the Probe

Then a designated researcher should guide the session so that the interaction of the participants with the probe follows the goal of each step of the user journey. At this point, it's important to observe participant's actions and listen to their opinions while they do the think-aloud. Also, at the end of a step from the user journey, it is necessary to give some time for participants to answer the questionnaire.

2.3 Post-session

When the participants complete the user journey, there is a final step to end the meeting. Ask participants to answer the final questionnaire to gather and compile their opinions and perceptions.

Step 3 – Post Technology Probe

After the execution of the study is time to analyze the data. Since the nature of the data collected from Technology Probe is qualitative, approaches to analyze it are interpretative data analysis or thematic analysis. It is up to the research team to choose their strategy. It is only important to keep in mind that the focus of the TP is to gather participant's feelings, experiences, suggestions and perceptions, being a method that focuses on the qualitative aspect.

The results of the ESE-TechProbe are mainly user feedback and an understatement of user experience. This can generate a list of technological proposal improvements or software requirements.

Conclusion

We hope this tutorial helps using the ESE-TechProbe and contribute to a better understanding of the Technology Probe Methodology. For questions and suggestions, please contact: galeno@cos.ufrj.br.

Related Institutions:

Further Information

NASCIMENTO, Luciana; GALENO, Larissa; PESSOA, Clinton Hudson; SILVA, Patricia Furtado; TRAVASSOS, Guilherme Horta. Uso de Technology Probe na Engenharia de Sistemas de Software para Saúde. In: CONGRESSO IBERO-AMERICANO EM ENGENHARIA DE SOFTWARE (CIBSE), 27. , 2024, Curitiba/PR. Anais [...]. Porto Alegre: Sociedade Brasileira de Computação, 2024 . p. 211-225. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/cibse.2024.28449>.

Appendix

Below will be described the questionnaires to used and adapted:

1. [Informed Consent Form \(ICF\)](#)
2. [Pre-session Questionnaire](#)
3. [Post-Journey Step Questionnaire](#)
4. [Post-session Questionnaire](#)
5. [Researcher Notes](#)

It can also be download from:

<https://ese-techprobe.vercel.app/documents.html>

Informed Consent Form (ICF)

I declare that I am over 18 years old and agree to participate in studies conducted by <include research team name/research team responsible> from <research team should specify the laboratory/ university>. These studies aim to understand software technology's feasibility, viability, and experience using the Technology Probe methodology.

Procedures

Various software technologies may be presented. I understand that I will be taught how technology works and asked to use it during the session organized by the researcher. In this session, some experimental methods will be applied, and I will be asked to complete some tasks to reflect on their use and evaluate them. I understand that once the session has ended, the opinions I expressed and the questionnaires I answered will be studied to understand the aspects of the software technology presented to me.

The researcher will conduct the study by collecting, analyzing, and reporting data collected throughout the session. I understand that I am not obligated to provide information regarding my performance in the session and that I may request the removal of my results from the study at any time without penalty. I understand that there will be no reward for participating in this study and that my decision not to participate will not negatively impact me. I also understand that once the data is collected and analyzed, my name will be removed from the data and will not be used during the analysis or in the presentation of the results.

Confidentiality

All information collected in this study is confidential and follows the principles of <research team should specify applicable data protection regulations, e.g., GDPR, LGPD>. My name will not be identified at any time. Likewise, I commit not to disclose my results until the study is completed and to maintain confidentiality regarding the techniques and documents presented that are part of the experiment.

Benefits and Right to Withdraw

I understand that this study does not pose any personal risk and that the benefits I will receive from participating are limited to learning about the proposed software technology. However, the researchers hope to gain insights into the software technology's feasibility, viability, and experience.

I understand that I am free to ask questions at any time or request that any personal information related to me not be included in the study. I am participating voluntarily, solely to contribute to the advancement and development of software technology.

Responsible

<complete with the name of the research team responsible>

<complete with the person affiliation>

Consent Statement

By signing below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood this form and voluntarily agree to participate in the study.

Participant's Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

For the research team to fill - ID: _____

Pre-session Questionnaire

Demographic questions

(examples of demographic questions that can be used in this session)

What is your age?

- 18–24 25–34 35–44 45–54 55+

What is your gender?

- Male Female Prefer not to say

Other: _____

What is your highest level of education?

- Primary Education Secondary Education Higher Education

Other: _____

How familiar are you with tools like...? *(describe a similar tool to your probe)*

- Not familiar Somewhat familiar Familiar Very familiar
-

Expectations

After hearing the explanation about the study context, tell us what your expectations are regarding the technology and its usage:

For the research team to fill - ID: _____

Post-Journey Step Questionnaire

<Complete with Journey Step Name>

Mark the level of satisfaction with the experience the <complete with probe name> offered:

How would you improve the experience the <complete with probe name> offers for this moment?
Feel free to write or draw ideas and suggestions.

For the research team to fill - ID: _____

Post-session Questionnaire (1)

What was your overall satisfaction with the <complete with probe name> you interacted with? Mark your level of satisfaction

Given the following adjectives, how would you describe the <complete with probe name>? Circle as many options you find appropriate

Pros
Accessible
Consistent
Desirable
Empowering
Fast
Helpful
Intuitive
Motivating
Novel
Relevant
Stimulating
Valuable

Cons
Annoying
Boring
Confusing
Dull
Frustrating
Hard to use
Ineffective
Old
Poor quality
Rigid
Stressful
Unattractive

For the research team to fill - ID: _____

Post-session Questionnaire (2)

Did anything catch your attention in any way while using the *<complete with probe name>*?

Would you like to change anything regarding the *<complete with probe name>*?

Feel free to write anything else you did not have the opportunity to expose regarding the *<complete with probe name>* or the study in other questions!

For the research team to fill - ID: _____

Researcher Notes (1)

Social (user experience; user feedback; user behaviors)

Design (co-creation; user suggestions)

Engineering (probe must be working properly; probe malfunction)

Researcher: _____

Researcher Notes (2)

Space for free annotations:

Researcher: _____